

BIOCHEMICAL STUDY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHRONIC VIRAL HEPATITIS WITH COMORBID COURSE OF CHRONIC GLOMERULONEPHRITIS

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Аннотация. Вторичные клубочковые поражения при вирусных гепатитах протекают медленно, однако у трети больных процесс неуклонно прогрессирует и проявляется нефротическим синдромом, ухудшает состояние больного с проявлениями почечной недостаточности. Цель данного исследования изучить клинические и биохимические аспекты поражения функционального состояния почек при хроническом вирусном гепатите В и С. В исследование включено 198 пациентов с положительными серологическими маркерами ВГВ и ВГС и клинико--лабораторными синдромами поражения почек.

Ключевые слова: Хронический гломерулонефрит, хронический гепатит В и С.

Annotation. Secondary glomerular lesions in viral hepatitis occur slowly, but in a third of patients the process progresses steadily and manifests as nephrotic syndrome, worsening the patient's condition with manifestations of renal failure. The purpose of this study is to study the clinical and biochemical aspects of the damage to the functional state of the kidneys in chronic viral hepatitis B and C. The study included 198 patients with positive serological markers of HBV and HCV and clinical-renal syndrome of kidney damage.

Key words: Chronic glomerulonephritis, chronic hepatitis B and C.

Relevance. Chronic viral hepatitis B, C, which occupies a dominant place among all liver diseases, is one of the most important problems of modern hepatology due to its widespread distribution and high incidence rate. According to WHO, there are about 15% of carriers of hepatitis B virus (HBV) in the world and 10% of carriers of viral hepatitis C (HCV) of the entire population of the globe [2,5].

In the pathogenesis of parenteral hepatitis, course and outcomes, the leading role is given to immune mechanisms. The characteristic "escape" of hepatitis viruses from "immune surveillance", due to the inferiority of the

immune response, determines the persistence of the pathogen and the formation of a chronic course of infection. Circulating immune complexes in chronic viral liver pathology can cause the appearance of extrahepatic lesions of organs and systems.

It is believed that the hepatitis B virus may play a role in the development of glomerulonephritis. As evidence of this position, the following are considered: an increased frequency of detection of markers of infection with the hepatitis B virus, and primarily HBsAg, among patients with various forms of glomerulonephritis; detection of HBsAg deposits in the glomeruli of the kidneys and immune complexes HBsAg - anti-HBs, which are of primary importance in kidney damage. According to some researchers, HBsAg carriage is regarded as a risk factor for the development of glomerulonephritis [6].

Among patients with hepatitis B with the presence of glomerulonephritis, its morphological variants are recorded: membranous, membranous-proliferative, endo - and extracapillary, etc.

The mechanism of renal damage associated with viral hepatitis B has not been fully determined. Several assumptions have been made related to: the direct effect of the HBsAg-anti-HBs immunocomplexes; immunocomplexes containing anti-HBc, HBeAg, anti-HBe; with the action of components of destroyed hepatocytes and autoantibodies produced on them during the disease process.

In the structure of renal pathology, one of the leading places belongs to glomerulonephritis (GN), due to the severity of complications, difficulties of diagnosis, imperfect therapy, and poor prognosis of most of its chronic forms. GN today is a kidney disease, which, in addition to the primary one, often acquires the significance of a secondary lesion that develops within the framework of a certain systemic or metabolic-endocrine pathology, the spectrum of which is extremely wide. The systemic nature of the process involving the kidneys is inherent in blood-borne viral hepatitis, in particular HBV and HCV.

In adults, secondary glomerular lesions due to viral hepatitis proceed slowly, but in a third of patients the process steadily progresses, may manifest as nephrotic syndrome, worsen the patient's condition with manifestations of renal failure, is difficult to respond to anti-inflammatory therapy, and requires the use of extracorporeal methods of treating immune complex pathology (plasmapheresis, hemosorption) [1,2].

The purpose of this study is to study the clinical and biochemical aspects of damage to the functional state of the kidneys in chronic viral hepatitis B and C.

Material and methods. The present study included 198 patients with positive serological markers of HBV and HCV and clinical and laboratory syndromes of kidney damage (glomerulonephritis). Among them, men accounted for 47.8% (95 people), women 52.2% (103 people). The average age of those examined was 52 ± 3.7 years.

To compare the course of the disease, glomerulonephritis associated with chronic viral hepatitis, the examination included 32 patients with glomerulonephritis who were not found to be infected with hepatitis viruses.

The study was conducted in the nephrology department of the Bukhara Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center.

When examining patients, anamnestic data was collected, anthropometric indicators were measured, body type was determined, the condition of organs and systems was assessed, and blood pressure was measured.

All subjects underwent a functional examination, a biochemical blood test with determination of the level of ALT, AST, bilirubin and its fractions, total protein and its fractions, the level of urea and creatinine, the glomerular filtration rate of GFR was determined (according to the SKD-EPI equation), a general urinalysis, with the determination daily proteinuria. In all those examined, markers of hepatitis B and C were determined using ELISA and also ultrasound examination of the kidneys and liver.

The diagnosis of chronic glomerulonephritis (CGn) was established on the basis of anamnestic and clinical-biochemical data: edema syndrome, high blood pressure, changes in the fundus characteristic of nephrogenic hypertension, increased urea and creatinine in the blood serum, hypoproteinemia, dysproteinemia, proteinuria (more than 1g/day) characteristic urinary sediment (hematuria, cylindruria) [3].

The examination of patients was carried out in accordance with the recommendations of WHO experts for the healthcare system [WHO, Geneva, 2012]. When carrying out our research, we complied with all ethical principles of medical research involving human subjects adopted by the Declaration of Helsinki of the World Medical Association in 1964 (latest addition at the 59th General Assembly of the World Medical Association in 2008 in Seoul).

Processing of the obtained data was carried out by the method of nonparametric statistics using a computer program. Correlations with $p < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

Results and discussion. The results of our survey showed the following data: the detection rate of chronic hepatitis B was 47%, chronic hepatitis C was 41.4%. 11.6% were found to be infected with a mixed infection, and markers of hepatitis B and C were determined (Table 1).

1 table

Frequency of detection of types of chronic hepatitis in patients with chronic glomerulonephritis (CGn)

	1 group CGn with HBV n=93	2nd group CGn with HCV n=82	3 group CGn with VG B+S n=23	Patients with and without chronic viral hepatitis n=32
Age	44,1±3,1	38,3 ±4,2	33,7±7	48,4±8,5
Man	52	40	14	11
Woman	41	42	9	21
Duration Currents(years): HGn, HVG	6,8±0,7 4,6±0,5	7,2±0,8 4,2±0,5	6,9±1,4 3,9±0,8	7,1±1,2

When analyzing the results of clinical and laboratory studies, the frequency of detection and severity of clinical symptoms of chronic glomerulonephritis and the level of laboratory markers of this disease in all groups of patients were studied. At the same time, the clinical manifestation of the disease was characterized by the development of nephrotic syndrome, hematuria, and arterial hypertension. We paid attention to pronounced peripheral edema, the presence of free fluid in the abdominal and pleural cavities, the level of increased blood pressure, and the severity of splenomegaly [4].

The functional capacity of the kidneys was assessed by serum creatinine levels and glomerular filtration rate. Kidney function is assessed by glomerular filtration rate (GFR). Calculation of GFR is mandatory. The most rational and reliable way to determine GFR is its automatic calculation in biochemical laboratories, which should produce two results - serum creatinine concentration and estimated GFR. We calculated GFR using the CKD-EPI method, taking into account the level of creatinine in the blood serum, race, gender and age of the patient.

The clinical picture of liver damage in the examined patients was assessed taking into account the syndromes of cytolysis (increased activity of ALT and

AST), cholestasis (increased levels of GGT, alkaline phosphatase, bilirubin), jaundice (increased total bilirubin due to its direct fraction). The results of urine analysis, the level and severity of proteinuria, hematuria in all groups were analyzed (table 2).

Table 2.

Clinical and laboratory parameters of patients with CG on the background of CVH

Indicators	1 group CGn with HBV n=93	2nd group CGn with HCV n=82	3 group CGn with VG B+S n=23	Patients with and without chronic viral hepatitis n=32
Peripheral edema (%)	65,6	41,2	90	58,3
Ascites (%)	29,1	33,6	46,7	12,6
Arterial hypertension (%)	25,3	26,6	31,2	41,3
Splenomegaly (%)	34,6	39,5	47,8	20,3
Proteinuria (g/day)	4,1±0.3	3,9±0.2	5,9±0.2	4,3±0.3
Total protein (g/l)	57,6±1.1	52,3±1.3	46,1±1.4	52,5±1.5
Albumin(g/l)	39,9±1.3	38,3±1.2	25,7±1.4	39,7±1.3
GFR ml	66,6±2.3	62,9±2.2	50,7±2.6	69.3±1.8
ALT (IU/l)	46,2±2.1	47,7±2.9	51,9±3.5	53,5±3.3
AST (IU/l)	48,4±1.2	49,1±1.8	61,2±1.5	40,4±1.9

Analysis of the results shows that the occurrence of clinical symptoms of chronic glomerulonephritis increases in patients with CGN-associated CVH. The severity of edema syndrome is more common in the group of CG patients with hepatitis B+C (90%). In patients in this group, the incidence of arterial hypertension also predominates in other groups [5-6].

The incidence of splenomegaly syndrome is greater in patients with CGN associated CVH (47.8%) than in patients with glomerulonephritis not infected with hepatitis B and C viruses (20.3%).

The analyzed results of biochemical tests show that the level of liver damage (according to the results of ALT and AST levels) is higher in patients with CGN-associated chronic hepatitis than in patients with glomerulonephritis not infected with hepatitis B and C viruses. Accordingly, one can see the level of

kidney damage. Since GFR indicators are low in patients with CGN associated CVH.

Conclusion. In CGN associated with CVH, a significant decrease in protein metabolism, GFR, and increased liver damage are observed in comparison with similar indicators for CGN without CVH association.

Comparison of blood protein metabolism indicators, the level of GFR and daily proteinuria revealed the following features of CGN associated with CVH: the most severe changes that contribute to the progression of CGN (hypoproteinemia, proteinuria, decreased GFR) are more typical for patients with CGN with the association of CGN C and B+C, in comparison with CHVG B and CHVG C.

In conclusion, it should be noted that kidney damage associated with the course of chronic viral hepatitis is quite common and may have different development mechanisms and diverse clinical and morphological manifestations. It is obvious that the awareness of infectious disease doctors and nephrologists in this field of medicine, their closer interaction in this direction is necessary for the diagnosis and treatment of this complex associated pathology.

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